

5 + 1 Keystone Behavioral as a Business Innovation Strategy Approach

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ABSTRACT: *The purpose of this study is to explore and demonstrate the importance of creating a culture of innovation and the use of innovation as a competitive business strategy by using the 5 + 1 behavioural keystone approach in dealing with rapid market changes. The research method used is to identify, measure and analyse the 5 + 1 behavioural keystone approach and the measurement of Report KPIs as a business innovation strategy approach. The study found that 5 + 1 behavioural keystone has an effect on the creation of a culture and innovation environment that is used as a business innovation strategy and high KPI reports also identify that the company has a high innovation culture.*

KEYWORDS: *5 + 1 Behavioural keystone, Strategic innovation approach, KPI Report, Innovation environment*

I. INTRODUCTION

Every company requires and carries out a process of innovation both in the process and in creating products and services provided to consumers. Innovation is not just a formula and a plan but has become a necessity in business. Businesses that want to develop and survive require innovation as a business strategy to be able to adapt to the rapidly changing marketplace. [6] explain that there are 5 innovation processes which include procurement, testing, studying market output and reactions, iterating, retesting, studying the final product and developing. Of course, creating and creating innovation within the company is not easy.

[6] state that innovation can fail because companies use the same process in managing innovative products with the main product, and do not use the right lens to observe unconscious market changes. By creating and using innovative creative ideas within the company as a competitive strategy, it will be able to prevent the company from going into bankruptcy or financial distress. The failure of innovation is also caused by a lack of support from management and the company for employees to form an innovation process. Of course, to achieve an innovation strategy, it is necessary to have supporting human resources and technology.

[5] explain that to be able to adjust and adapt to the company's innovation strategy, it is necessary to increase innovation prowess and use the creativity of company employees. [6] explain to support the creation of creativity in the company, it is important to build a pleasant atmosphere to trigger creative ideas and capture and test the resulting creative ideas. By conducting testing and capturing ideas from employees, it will create a creative environment and support employees to have a culture of innovation in the business.

[2] explain that the factor of habit formation is caused by personality (internal) and the environment (external). Personality which is an internal factor of an employee is one of the factors that is difficult to change but the environment which is a supporting factor for the creation of employee habits can be created and changed by the company.

By supporting the innovation culture and habits within the company, management and leaders must be able to create a culture of innovation in employees' daily activities. According to [5] companies must be able to provide

management activities and information-sharing activities to achieve optimal innovation potential for employees. management and leaders must be able to create a culture of innovation in the daily activities of employees. According to [5], companies must be able to provide management activities and information-sharing activities to achieve optimal innovation potential for employees. management and leaders must be able to create a culture of innovation in the daily activities of employees. According to [5], companies must be able to provide management activities and information-sharing activities to achieve optimal innovation potential for employees.

The innovation environment and innovation culture also require support from leaders and managers as the main supporting factors for the innovation culture in business. [2] state that leaders are the architect of ideas. Being the architect of ideas means a leader does not only act as the leader of the company but can create a work environment that helps employees engage in innovative behavior that is part of their daily work. Determining and selecting employees who have high potential for creativity and innovative ideas for the company is also the key to the success of business innovation. [2] in supporting employees to have the potential for innovation and creativity can use the 5 +1 keystone behavior approach, namely focus, connect, tweak, select, stealthstorm, and persist. [5]. Of course, in enhancing a culture of innovation and creativity and creating great ideas, leadership is needed that can create a culture of innovation and bring employees to excel in 5 + 1 keystone behavior.

The purpose of this study is to explore and demonstrate the importance of creating a culture of innovation and the use of innovation as a business competitive strategy using the 5 + 1 behavioral keystone approach in dealing with rapid market changes. This study also discusses the impact of increasing innovation performance by creating a behavior and a culture of innovation in business. Companies must be able to create and measure a culture of innovation which is an external factor that can be created by the company to influence employee innovation habits. The impact of improving employee performance will be seen through the willingness and willingness of employees and management to participate in creating a culture of business innovation as a focus and business strategy.

II. RESEARCH METHODS

This research will use qualitative research methods by identifying, measuring and analyzing the 5 + 1 behavioral keystone approach and measuring the KPI Report matrix. This research will be conducted in manufacturing companies with a minimum number of employees of 100 people. The number of samples used in this study was 10 companies. Data collection techniques by conducting interviews, observation, and documentation. After collecting data and analyzing data, this research will also conduct triangulation testing of validity and reliability to ensure the validity of the data by comparing information by means of triangulation of methods and triangulation of situations in the 5 + 1 behavioral keystone approach that includes focus, connect, tweak, select, stealthstorm, and persist will be developed into corporate innovation strategies. According to [5], corporate strategic innovations include:

Table 1. Strategic framework as a strategic business innovation approach

Input	Output
Develop a positive reinforcement system (focus)	Motivate individuals to participate in innovative behavior
Supports I-Teams (stealthstorm)	Focusing entrepreneurship through new organizations within the company
Support and maintain an entrepreneurial environment (connect)	Helping innovative-minded people to reach their full potential
Providing intra-capital for corporate entrepreneurs (tweak)	Awarding corporate entrepreneur
Reduce organizational boundaries (select)	Encourage employees to see the company through the perspective of the board of directors
Facilitating top management support (Persist)	Educate employees about corporate entrepreneurship

(Source: Strategic framework for increasing corporate internal innovation performance)

The initial stage in this research will identify the innovation process and the business environment to be included and categorized into the Strategic framework input factors. After identifying and categorizing the process, the next step is to analyze the resulting output of each process the company carries out in support of the creation of a culture and environment of innovation as a business strategy. [6] explain that in measuring innovation, companies can use innovation accounting. Innovation accounting is part of innovation management and includes 3 KPIs namely, Report KPIs, Regulatory KPIs and Global KPIs. In this study, researchers will use the KPI Report to measure the culture of innovation and the performance of Innovation Teams (I-Teams) on the impact of the resulting innovation.

Table 2. Report KPI Matrix for Innovation Strategy

Activity Metrics	Impact Metrics
Number of ideas generated	Hypotheses developed
Number of ideas selected	The minimum failure criteria applied
Assumptions identified	

(Source: The Corporate Startup (Success Formula for Established Companies in Developing Innovation Ecosystems), 2018)

In the activity metric, the number of ideas generated discusses how many ideas are generated by employees in daily innovation activities. The number of ideas selected discusses how many ideas are selected and used by the company for the resulting innovation idea activities, while the identified assumptions discuss the assumptions generated through the selection of innovative ideas and are used as the basis for hypotheses to be developed in the impact matrix and minimum failure criteria. applied by management and the company.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To determine the relationship between 5 + 1 behavioral keystone to the innovation process within the company, this study uses identification and categorization for each activity in the company into the strategic framework as a

basis for analyzing data. After the data is collected, the data will be represented through descriptive statistics to see an overview of the events through the results of data processing the relationship between 5 + 1 keystone behavior (Strategic framework) which will be used as a strategic innovation corporate (KPI Report). Descriptive statistics will also describe 5 +1 keystone behavioral elements which include focus, connect, tweak, select, stealthstorm, and persist. High matrix test results indicate that management is successful in focusing employees to have a level of focus on innovation goals and ideas that are in line. [2] focus on discussing how management can control employees who have complete freedom to innovate and often have random ideas that are not important in business and may end up dividing their attention among various small side projects that ultimately do not produce results. anything to focus on strategy and business goals through innovations and ideas that are created.

Based on the analysis of the strategic framework and KPI Report matrix, it can be concluded that, in the first point which is input process that discuss about developing a positive reinforcement system (focus) from the five companies, the average score is 4 points with an output of 3 which indicates that the company helps employees in creating focus environment through clear rules and division of departments and job desks. The focus in terms of innovation is to provide direction and limits of freedom at the same time so that innovators only aim for one goal, namely to innovate and in line with the goals and values of the company. Creating a focus on innovators within the company will reduce the freedom to work but will create a work scope that supports and directs innovators only to think and look for innovations that are in line and have value for the business (fundamental business values).

The second point regarding to stealthstorm (Input Supports I-Teams) gets a 4 point with an output value of 2 which explains that in the five companies, employees often cannot avoid organizational politics which are often referred to as (stealthstorming rules). Of course, stealthstorming rules can cause someone who has ideas and innovations to spend some of his time dealing with other stakeholders and employees who are involved in organizational politics. Within the company, innovation ideas are often rejected and fail to develop because the individuals and departments that innovate do not take part in the company's politics.

Output Supporting and maintaining an entrepreneurial environment (connect) getting an input value of 4 with an output of 3 companies providing support to employees to build relationships and relationships with external parties and also with the outside world to be able to get and create new innovative ideas that will be useful in the future front. Input tweak is assessed by looking at the provision of intra-capital for corporate entrepreneurs. In this section

Output Reduces organizational boundaries (select)

Input Facilitates top management support (Persist)

Output Educate employees about corporate entrepreneurship

Connect discusses how employees can connect with the outside world and not only focus on problems and isolated in the office [2]. High connect valuation indicates that management and employees can connect and manage external information to be used as ideas and innovative ideas in the business. [5] one of the significant contributions of entrepreneurial behavior is a learning process that will strengthen the ability of employees to analyze the market and formulate it into new products. The tweak or pinch explains that management as architects of innovation must help people constantly test and challenge their ideas, exposing them to frequent feedback and promoting a culture of rapid learning and experimentation.

A high matrix evaluation of select indicates that employees and management are able to filter out bad ideas and ideas. This selection is not only discarding ideas that have the potential to harm the company but also as learning material for employees to create wrong ideas and innovative ideas in the future. [6] explain that choosing an innovation idea and paying attention to deficiencies in an idea has an important function in the success of the innovation process and portfolio management in the future. After building an environment of innovation and entrepreneurship, management must also be able to form and support Innovation Teams (I-Teams). According to [5], I-Teams is an internal company team formulated for the purpose of creating new innovations. I-Teams has a

relationship with stealthstorm; stealthstorm discusses how management and companies should be able to minimize and separate the relationship between political interests and innovation [2].

According to [2] Persist is the connecting key of the 5 keystone behaviors because the realization of focus, connect, tweak, select, and stealthstorm requires management determination and persistence to ensure the creation of a culture of innovation within the company. [5] explain that management must have the right level of control and trust in the innovation and entrepreneurial process to create ideas and innovative products. In addition to the 5+ 1 behavioral keystone in this study, the KPI Report analysis also plays an important role in the success and magnitude of the innovation environment in business.

According to [6], a high activity matrix indicates that innovative ideas and ideas are quite large in the company and the innovation process is often carried out. Not only as a measure of how many ideas and innovative ideas are created but the activity matrix also shows how far ideas and ideas have progressed. In addition to the activity matrix, employees also need to determine and evaluate an impact matrix that discusses the number of products tested and the criteria for success and failure of innovati activity. The impact matrix with larger failures shows that the ideas and ideas created by employees and the innovation process are not running effectively and efficiently.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the tests that have been done, it can be concluded that by creating a culture of innovation and through the support of 5 + 1 keystone behavior influencing the creation of a culture and innovation environment that is used as a business innovation strategy and a high KPI report also identifies that the company has a high innovation culture. By using and building a culture of innovation within the company, the success of the company will be even greater, the impact of the innovation culture variables within the company also increases the value and performance of the company as seen from the average value of success and the increase in company value. [5] state that using innovative strategies will provide benefits for companies where entrepreneurship can facilitate the company's innovation process and culture and can be used as a competitive strategy and company competitiveness. In addition, this study also aims to provide an overview and input for companies to create a culture of innovation that can be formed and supported by 5 + 1 keystone behaviors and to measure the innovation process within the company as measured by the KPI Report. The creation of a culture of innovation that is used as a business innovation strategy will create a strong and innovative business.

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